

Active phase and amplitude temperature control method for cryostat: A case in the thermodynamic temperature international comparison system

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ABSTRACT Highly stable temperature control is critical for many applications, which is usually realized by a cryostat. However, the cryocooler of the cryostat, such as the pulse tube refrigerator, generates a regular sinusoidal temperature fluctuation at the second cold due to its working principle, which also downwardly transfers to all places. To establish a highly stable temperature environment, an active phase and amplitude control method for suppressing temperature fluctuation is proposed in this paper, by which the optimal phase and amplitude can be predicted in theory. To verify the performance of the method, simulation was carried out in the present work. Firstly, thermal response experiments were conducted in the thermodynamic temperature international comparison cryostat at about 3.7K. Secondly, the construction of the transfer function and thermal response model from the second cold to the comparison copper block was undertaken. Thirdly, utilizing the model, active temperature control current was introduced along the cold transfer path, and optimal phase and amplitude values for both single-stage and multi-stage joint temperature control were determined. The simulation results have good agreement with the predicted values. Besides, it also shows that multi-stage joint temperature control can suppress the temperature fluctuation of the comparison copper block from 3.3mK to 0.15mK with 95.4% suppression rate. This study's findings hold promise for enabling highly stable temperature control in future comparisons of thermodynamic temperature data.

KEYWORDS Temperature fluctuation suppression; Cryostat; Thermal response; Active temperature control current

1. Introduction

Cryogenics plays a pivotal role in various critical domains, including fusion energy reactors, superconducting magnets, quantum computing, and large-scale engineering projects [1-3]. The precise measurement of cryogenic thermodynamic temperatures [4, 5] and the establishment of international comparison systems for cryogenics [6, 7] necessitate exceedingly stringent criteria for ensuring stability within the measurement environments.

Traditionally, cryogenic systems rely on liquid helium or cryocoolers as primary cooling sources to deliver the necessary cooling capacity [8-10]. However, liquid helium is costly, and cryostats using it as a cooling source encounter discontinuities. Consequently, closed cycle cryocoolers have gained prominence in recent years as the preferred cold source for cryostats. Among these, the widely adopted 4K pulse-tube cooler falls into the reheat type cooler category. This cooler operates with a cyclic expansion of its working fluid, typically helium, leading to inherent temperature fluctuations [10]. At 5K, these fluctuations can reach up to 200 millikelvin, failing to meet the stringent stability requirements crucial for experimental conditions. The utilization of a pulse-tube cooler in a cryostat necessitates addressing the challenge posed by its inherent temperature fluctuations. To mitigate these fluctuations originating from the cryocooler itself, numerous researchers often employ methods based on heat capacity and thermal resistance to achieve temperature stabilization and attenuation.

1.1. Heat capacity method

The heat capacity method refers to installing materials with high heat capacity at low temperatures below the cold head of cryocooler, such as helium, lead, rare earth alloys like ErNi, among others. Researchers have implemented various strategies employing this method to mitigate temperature fluctuations. Li *et al.* [11] affixed a copper canister to the cold head of a 4K-stage GM cryocooler, observing a reduction in temperature fluctuation from 530mK to 54mK at 4.2K. Okidono *et al.* [12] installed a copper cylinder filled with high-pressure helium below the cold head, achieving a decrease in temperature fluctuation from 300mK to 10mK at 3.8K and 4.5K, with inflation pressures of 90 and 60 atm, respectively. Webber *et al.* [13] applied a helium damper

beneath a 4K Gifford-McMahon cryocooler, suppressing intrinsic temperature oscillations and shortening cooling times below 10K. Guy *et al.* [14] conducted temperature attenuation experiments utilizing a combined thermal link composed of lead, supplemented by copper and stainless steel sheets. Their results demonstrated that the thermal link could diminish cold head temperature fluctuations from 200mK to 1mK at 5K. Additionally, You *et al.* [15] interposed a 35mm diameter and 16mm thick ErNi plate between the cryocooler's cold head and the detector. ErNi exhibits a heat capacity of $0.2\text{J}/\text{cm}^3\cdot\text{K}$ at 5K, ten times that of lead ($0.02\text{J}/\text{cm}^3\cdot\text{K}$) [16]. This intervention resulted in reducing the detector's temperature fluctuation from 290mK to 8mK at 4.2K.

1.2. Thermal resistance method

The thermal resistance method involves incorporating materials with high thermal resistance at low temperatures between the cold head and the operating platform to attenuate temperature fluctuations. Examples of such materials include oxygen-free copper, polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), glass fiber reinforced plastic (FRP), and holmium copper (HoCu_2). Researchers have explored this method to mitigate temperature variations effectively. Gao *et al.* [17,18] utilized high-conductivity oxygen-free copper as a thermal link positioned between the cold head and the flange, achieving substantial suppression of fluctuations. Dong *et al.* [19] employed a 45mm diameter and 2mm thick PTFE thermal link to diminish cryocooler fluctuations, observing a reduction to less than 2mK from an initial 300mK at 4.2K. Hasegawa *et al.* [20, 21] conducted experiments using FRP thermal links, with diameters of 45mm and thicknesses of 0.5mm and 1.0mm, placed between the cryocooler's cold head and a copper block. The results indicated that both thicknesses of the thermal links attenuated temperature fluctuations from 200mK to 50mK at the lowest temperatures. However, they noted that the installation of thermal links had an impact on the cold transfer of the system. Furthermore, Wang *et al.* [22] implemented HoCu_2 , possessing thermal conductivity three orders of magnitude larger than copper near their operating temperatures [23, 24], as a thermal link between the second stage cryocooler and the second active shield in a 3K cryostat. This intervention led to a reduction in temperature fluctuation from 4mK to 0.3mK.

1.3. Active temperature control method

The aforementioned methods effectively mitigate temperature fluctuations. However, once the thermal link structure is installed within the system, it remains unalterable, leading to a fixed temperature control effect. These approaches, known as passive temperature control methods, lack the capability to adjust to disturbances or fluctuations within the system. To enhance temperature control capabilities, scholars have introduced active temperature control methods primarily focused on suppressing fluctuations in cold head temperatures. Soso *et al.* [25, 26] employed linear system theory to develop a dynamic model that analyzed the thermal response of the cryocooler. This analysis provided an efficient approach for designing temperature controllers. Similarly, Bhatt *et al.* [27] established the transfer function of the cryocooler and determined optimal proportional-integral (PI) control parameters for the system. In our prior research led by Gao *et al.* [28, 29], active temperature control currents were applied within the context of single-pressure refractive-index gas thermometry. Employing an established thermal response model, the optimal phase angle of the active current was identified, resulting in a further reduction of temperature fluctuation from 5.2mK to 3.3mK.

1.4. Main content of this paper

While many previous studies have primarily concentrated on the feedback mechanism aimed at suppressing temperature fluctuations specifically at the cryocooler's cold head, a comprehensive investigation into active temperature control necessitates the development of an encompassing model spanning from the cold head to the temperature control terminal. For a thorough examination of temperature transfer processes and the observation of temperature fluctuations at the temperature control terminal, it becomes essential to construct a comprehensive model that covers the entire trajectory of temperature control. This holistic model will facilitate a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics involved in temperature transfer processes and enable the observation of temperature fluctuations at various points within the temperature control pathway. Subsequently, based on this comprehensive understanding, an optimal active temperature control scheme for the system can be determined.

This study conducts an active phase and amplitude temperature control method investigation within the 5K-24.5K temperature range system established by the Technical Institute of Physics and Chemistry, Chinese Academy of Sciences, focused on thermodynamic temperature international comparison. In section 2, we describe the apparatus, the proposed methods and response characteristic experiment. In section 3, the building and verification of thermal response transfer model are presented. In section 4, we discuss the simulated results of single stage temperature control and multistage joint temperature control. A conclusion is made in section 5.

2. Response characteristic experiment of cryostat

2.1. cryostat

Fig. 1 illustrates a schematic diagram of the cryostat, which is used to facilitate the international comparison of thermodynamic temperature in 5K-24.5K temperature region. The cooling mechanism of the system relies on a GM cryocooler with the model number Sumitomo's RP-182B2S-F100. This cryocooler provides a cooling capacity of 36W@48K for the first cold stage and 1.5W@4.2K for the second cold.

The gradual transfer of the cooling capacity from the second cold extends to the comparison copper block via the thermal pathway encompassing the thermal link, second flange, and third flange. Simultaneously, temperature fluctuations also propagate along this pathway. During the execution of international comparisons involving low-temperature thermodynamic measurements, ensuring a highly stable temperature environment for the comparison copper block becomes imperative to minimize experimental discrepancies and errors in the comparison process.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the international comparison system in 5K-24.5K temperature region

2.2. Active phase and amplitude temperature control method

The temperature fluctuations at the second cold exhibit a predictable sinusoidal pattern. As the cooling capability cascades downward, under the assumption of disregarding additional disturbances, the temperature fluctuations at each respective location should also maintain a regular sinusoidal fluctuation pattern. To establish a highly stable temperature environment conducive to the comparison copper block's precision, an approach involves introducing a current along the path from the second cold to the comparison copper block. This method aims to achieve the target temperature and suppress temperature fluctuations, thereby realizing effective temperature control at target temperature. Building upon and refining the concept from our previous work [28, 29], this research endeavors to be more comprehensive, employing simplified experiments and optimizing multiple parameters.

2.2.1. Differences between our previous and the present method

The Fig. 2 demonstrates the similarities and differences between the active phase and amplitude temperature control method presented in this paper and our previous work.

(1) In our previous research, we utilized a direct current (DC) power supply for heating to achieve the desired temperature and employed a separate alternating current (AC) power supply for temperature control. In the new method, we have simplified the experiment by utilizing a single power source for both temperature elevation and control purposes.

(2) In our previous research, we sought the optimal phase angle for an added AC power source to match the temperature fluctuations of the second cold, aiming to mitigate its variations. In the

new method, we not only search for the optimal phase angle but also investigate the best amplitude to achieve a greater degree of temperature fluctuation attenuation.

(3) In our past experiment, the generation of the AC was complex, relying on intermittent measurements and storage of temperatures in the LabVIEW™ software as a reference. In the new method, we generate a sine wave current with phase angles from 0° to 360° every half an hour or shorter intervals. After the current phase completes a full cycle, we identify the phase angle corresponding to the minimal temperature fluctuation at the copper block as the optimal phase. This optimal phase is then fed back to the power signal, enabling continuous output based on this signal to adaptively search for the current phase. The present new method is more simply to implement in practice. The procedure for finding the amplitude is similar in nature.

(4) In our previous research, the current was only applied to the second cold. In the new method, we apply active temperature control current to the second cold, the second flange, and the third flange, aiming to achieve multi-stage precision temperature control.

Fig. 2. The similarities and differences between previous method and new method in this work

2.2.2. The proposed methodology

In the present method, the phase and amplitude of the actively superimposed current ΔQ_{heat} used to eliminate temperature fluctuations can be calculated using the following formula. The heat balance equation for the second cold head can be written as following.

$$MC \frac{d(T_{\text{aim}} + \Delta T)}{dt} = Q_{\text{heat}} + \Delta Q_{\text{heat}} + Q_{\text{cold}} + \Delta Q_{\text{cold}} + Q_{\text{leak}} + \Delta Q_{\text{leak}} \quad (1)$$

where M is the quality of the material at the temperature control position, kg; C is the heat capacity of material, J/(kg·K); T_{aim} is the average temperature of aim temperature after heating, K; Q_{heat} is the heat from the heater, W; Q_{cold} is the cooling capacity from the cryocooler, W; Q_{leak} is the total heat leakage from surroundings by convection, conduction, and radiation, W. X_i means the stable part of X , while ΔX_i is the fluctuation part of X_i , $\Delta X_i = \Delta X_i(t)$.

Actually, equation (1) is equivalent to the following three equations (2), (3), (4), the former one is accounting for to the stable temperature reached, while the latter two is accounting for the temperature fluctuation. For equation (3), it means we add a fluctuation heat with zero amplitude, by which we can estimated the fluctuation cold capacity ΔQ_{heat} and ΔQ_{leak} from thermal response experiment. Then we can use equation (4) to reduce the ΔT as much as possible, for which the limit in theory is that $\Delta T \equiv 0$.

$$\text{stable: } MC \frac{d(T_{\text{aim}})}{dt} = Q_{\text{heat}} + Q_{\text{cold}} + Q_{\text{leak}} \equiv 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{initial temperature fluctuation: } MC \frac{d(\Delta T_{\text{initial}})}{dt} = \Delta Q_{\text{cold}} + \Delta Q_{\text{leak}} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{final temperature fluctuation: } MC \frac{d(\Delta T_{\text{final}})}{dt} = \Delta Q_{\text{heat}} + \Delta Q_{\text{cold}} + \Delta Q_{\text{leak}} \rightarrow 0 \quad (4)$$

where ΔQ_{heat} and $\Delta T_{\text{initial}}$ can be represented by the sine wave formula (5).

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta Q_{\text{heat}} &= \Delta Q_0 \sin(2\pi ft + \varphi) \\ \Delta T_{\text{initial}} &= \Delta T_0 \sin(2\pi ft + \varphi_0)\end{aligned}\quad (5)$$

where φ is the phase angle of Q_{heat} and φ_0 is the phase angle of temperature.

Usually, the heat fluctuation caused by heat leakage is very small when the temperature is below 25 K, so it can be neglected. Combined equations (3), (4) and (5), we obtain equation (6).

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta Q_{\text{heat}} + \Delta Q_{\text{cold}} &\approx 0, \text{ i.e.,} \\ \Delta Q_0 \sin(2\pi ft + \varphi) &= -MC \frac{d\Delta T_{\text{initial}}}{dt} = -MC\Delta T_0 \times 2\pi f \times \cos(2\pi ft + \varphi_0)\end{aligned}\quad (6)$$

Then the optimal phase and amplitude of the temperature-controlling current can be estimated based on the relationship between sine and cosine functions, as shown in the following equations.

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta Q_0 &= 2\pi fMC\Delta T_0 \\ \varphi &= \varphi_0 + \frac{3}{2}\pi, \quad \Delta\varphi = \varphi - \varphi_0 = 270^\circ\end{aligned}\quad (7)$$

From the above formula, it can be derived that, theoretically, the optimal amplitude of the temperature-controlling current can be determined based on data such as the material quality at the temperature control point and the initial temperature fluctuations. The optimal phase of the temperature-controlling current differs from the phase of the initial temperature fluctuations at the temperature control point by 270° . This paper will first conduct simulated research and analysis on the above results, followed by experimental research and validation.

2.3. Response characteristic experiment

Initially, it's essential to establish the temperature transfer relationship from the second cold to the comparison copper block. At the lowest temperature of the system, a thermal response experiment of " the cold source (the second cold) - the transfer pathway (comprising the second flange and third flange) - the temperature control core (the comparison copper block) " was conducted. This experiment facilitated the observation of temperature changes in the second cold, the second flange, the third flange, and the comparison copper block in response to alterations in the system's thermal input. By gathering and analyzing this dataset, a thermal response model encompassing the temperature transfer relationship from the second cold to the comparison copper block was formulated. Subsequently, research efforts were directed towards investigating methods for suppressing temperature fluctuations within this thermal pathway.

Fig. 3. Schematic diagram of the thermal response experiment

During the thermal response experiment, two aerospace-grade heaters with resistance values of $19\ \Omega$ and $97.5\ \Omega$ at low temperatures were precisely installed at the second flange and third flange to apply pulsed current. The pulsed current was supplied by two YOKOGAWA GS200 power sources. To monitor temperature variations with high sensitivity, highly responsive temperature sensors cernox, identified by their serial numbers X172548, X172520, X172747, and X172116, were strategically placed at the second cold, the second flange, the third flange, and the comparison copper block. Temperature data from these sensors were collected using four Keithley 2002 digital multi-meters, each dedicated to a specific sensor. The collection timing was synchronized using a JDS6600 signal generator, enabling simultaneous temperature data collection at various positions.

The coordination of signal control, data acquisition, and storage procedures was managed using a computer setup. Fig. 3 illustrates the experimental schematic.

Table 1 presents details regarding the model, serial numbers, and precision specifications of the experimental apparatus employed in the thermal response experiment.

Table 1

Experimental equipment in the thermal response experiment.

Serial number	Name	Model	Number	Accuracy
1	digital multimeter	Keithley2002	4	2.5ppm
2	Power	YOKOGAWA GS200	2	0.03%
3	signal generator	JDS6600	1	20ppm
4	sensor	Cernox (serial number: X172548、X172520、X172747、X172116)	4	5mK@4K

During the thermal response experiment, a pulse current of 120mA¹ was applied to the second flange, resulting in a heating power of 288mW. Simultaneously, the third flange received a pulse current of 15mA² generating a heating power of 22mW. The investigation aimed to assess whether the sequence of heating activation of the heaters affected the ultimate stabilized temperature of the system. Three distinct experiment groups were conducted and are outlined in Table 2. (1) The initial activation of pulse current was directed to the second flange. Once the system temperature stabilized, the pulse current was then applied to the third flange to achieve the final stabilized temperature of the system. (2) The initial activation of pulse current was directed to the third flange. Following stabilization of the system temperature, the pulse current was then applied to the second flange to achieve the final stabilized temperature of the system. (3) Pulse currents were simultaneously applied to both the second flange and third flange. This approach aimed to assess the temperature of the system after stabilization under these conditions.

Table 2

Heating sequences and heating of thermal response experiments.

Serial number	Heating sequences	Second flange heating Q_2 , current I_2 , heater resistance R_2	Third flange heating Q_3 , current I_3 , heater resistance R_3
1	H_2 first and then H_3		
2	H_3 first and then H_2	288mW, 120mA, 19Ω	22mW, 15mA, 97.5Ω
3	H_2 and H_3 together		

3. Thermal response transfer model

3.1. Mathematical model

The analysis of experimental outcomes from three distinct groups with varied heating sequences aims to scrutinize the potential impact of the heater's activation sequence on the ultimate stabilized temperature of the system. Take the temperature of the third flange T_3 as an example, the experimental results are shown in the Fig. 4 and the Table 3.

From the results in Fig. 4 and Table 3, it can be found that the heating sequences of heater H_2 and H_3 has nearly no effect³ (<0.4%) on the final temperature change of the third flange. The difference in temperature change caused by heater H_2 or H_3 on the third flange T_3 during the heating process is also not significant, as expected.

Since the heating sequences of the heater does not affect the final stabilized temperature of the system, the third group experimental data (i.e., two heaters heated at the same time) is chosen for

¹ The current limit of the power supply device is 200mA, and any current that does not exceed the range can also be selected.

² Because the third flange is close to the copper block, the heat can't be too large. According to previous experimental experience, the current here is generally not more than 20mA.

³ If waited long enough time, there is no difference in theory.

the transfer function construction to reduce the data analysis and simplify the model. Following the simultaneous application of pulse current in both the second flange and third flange, the resulting temperature variations observed in the second cold, the second flange, the third flange, and the comparison copper block are depicted in Fig. 5.

Fig. 4. temperature response of third flange T_3 under different heating sequences

Table 3

Temperature variation of third flange T_3 under different heating sequences.

Heating sequences	Temperature change after heating of H_2	Temperature change after heating of H_3	Total temperature change
H_2 first and then H_3	0.398K	0.338K	0.736K
H_3 first and then H_2	0.373K	0.360K	0.733K
H_2 and H_3 together	/	/	0.749K

Fig. 5. Temperature response of each position when H_2 and H_3 heated together

Under pulsed current, the temperature response can be expressed as a sum of exponential decay as shown in the following equation [32].

$$T(t) = A_0 + A_1 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_1}}\right) + A_2 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_2}}\right) \quad (8)$$

where A_0 , A_1 , and A_2 are the fitting parameters; t is the time, s; τ_1 and τ_2 are the response time, s.

To establish a temperature response model of high precision, a second-order response equation was selected for the fitting process. The outcomes of this fitting process are presented in the subsequent equation.

$$T_1 = 3.534 + 0.209 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{143.160}}\right) + 5.349 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{525155.694}}\right) \quad (9)$$

$$T_2 = 4.195 + 0.335 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{132.664}}\right) + 0.058 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{2080.467}}\right) \quad (10)$$

$$T_3 = 4.061 + 0.523 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{186.239}}\right) + 0.207 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{622.736}}\right) \quad (11)$$

$$T_4 = 4.158 + 0.499 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{193.850}}\right) + 0.182 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{664.556}}\right) \quad (12)$$

Fig. 6. Temperature fluctuation and frequency after stabilization

Following the stabilization of temperature, noticeable sinusoidal fluctuations become apparent in both the second cold and the second flange. The temperature fluctuations and the frequency obtained by Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) analysis are depicted in the Fig. 6. These fluctuations arise due to the operational principle of the cryocooler, causing periodic temperature oscillations in the second cold. The thermal link between the second flange and the second cold is established using oxygen-free copper, renowned for its exceptionally high thermal conductivity at low temperatures. This robust thermal connection facilitates a significant transmission of temperature fluctuations, contributing to the conspicuous sinusoidal temperature oscillations observed in the second flange. However, the temperature fluctuations observed in the third flange and the comparison copper block do not exhibit notable sinusoidal patterns. This absence of distinct sinusoidal fluctuations can be attributed to the greater distance from the second cold, resulting in a weaker

effect of temperature fluctuation transmission. Furthermore, the presence of background noise diminishes the apparent sinusoidal characteristics of the temperature fluctuations.

The temperature fluctuation of the second cold and the second flange is computed based on the peak-to-peak value of the sinusoidal wave. For the third flange and the comparison copper block, the temperature fluctuation is determined by calculating the difference between extreme values observed after the system stabilizes. These values are detailed in Table 4. For the sake of readability, the data presented in the paper is rounded to three decimal places. However, during simulation, a precision of six decimal places is employed to ensure accurate and detailed simulation results.

Table 4

Temperature and temperature fluctuation at different position.

Position	Second cold	Second flange	Third flange	Comparison cooper block
initial temperature	3.534 K	4.195 K	4.061K	4.158 K
stable temperature	3.755 K	4.563 K	4.781 K	4.828 K
temperature fluctuation (peak-to-peak)	312.1 mK	5.4 mK	3.6 mK	3.3 mK

Once stabilized, the temperature profiles of the second cold T_1' and second flange T_2' can be expressed using sinusoidal wave functions, as depicted in the following equations.

$$T_1' = T_{1,0}' + \Delta T_1 \sin(2\pi ft) = 3.755 + 0.156 \times \sin(10.82t) \quad (13)$$

$$T_2' = T_{2,0}' + \Delta T_2 \sin(2\pi ft + \varphi) = 4.563 + 0.003 \times \sin(10.83t + 4.076) \quad (14)$$

where $T_{1,0}'$, $T_{2,0}'$ means the stable temperature, K; ΔT_1 , ΔT_2 means temperature fluctuation, mK; f means the frequency, Hz; t means time, s; φ means phase angle (radian).

Fig. 7. Thermal response transfer relationship

Fig. 7 illustrates the cold, heat and temperature transfer relationship between the second cold, second flange, third flange, comparison copper block and two heaters.

G_1 symbolizes the transfer of cold from the second cold to the second flange, presented as the quotient between the Laplace transform of the stabilized temperature of the second flange⁴, denoted as T_2 , and the coldness of the second cold denoted as Q_1 .

$$G_1 = \frac{L(T_2' - T_{2,0}')}{L(Q_1)} = \frac{L(0.003 \times \sin(10.83x + 4.076))}{L\left(MC \frac{dT_1}{dt}\right)} = \frac{0.237s + 1.371}{18.624s} \quad (15)$$

where M denotes the mass of the second cold, $M=1.6$ kg. C denotes the heat capacity of oxygen-free copper at measurement temperature, taken as 0.07 J/(kg·K).

G_2 symbolizes the transfer of temperature from the second flange to the third flange, presented as the ratio between the Laplace transform of the temperature response in the third flange, denoted as T_3 , and the temperature response in the second flange, denoted as T_2 .

⁴ The transfer function does not consider the temperature after stability, but only focuses on temperature and its fluctuation resulting from the transfer

$$G_2 = \frac{L(T_3 - T_{3,0})}{L(T_2 - T_{2,0})} = \frac{L\left(0.523 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{186.239}}\right) + 0.207 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{622.736}}\right)\right)}{L\left(0.335 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{132.664}}\right) + 0.058 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{2080.467}}\right)\right)} \quad (16)$$

$$= \frac{100607864.404s^3 + 1008394.371s^2 + 1981.608s + 0.731}{81893963.052s^3 + 616885.608s^2 + 1024.564s + 0.394}$$

G_3 characterizes the transfer of temperature from the third flange to the comparison copper block, represented by the ratio between the Laplace transform of the temperature response observed in the comparison copper block, denoted as T_4 , and the temperature response observed in the third flange, denoted as T_3 .

$$G_3 = \frac{L(T_4 - T_{4,0})}{L(T_3 - T_{3,0})} = \frac{L\left(0.499 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{193.850}}\right) + 0.182 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{664.556}}\right)\right)}{L\left(0.523 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{186.239}}\right) + 0.207 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{622.736}}\right)\right)} \quad (17)$$

$$= \frac{42540081.899s^3 + 375701.022s^2 + 917.651s + 0.681}{46958513.762s^3 + 407032.591s^2 + 991.737s + 0.731}$$

G_4 and G_5 delineate the heat transfer originating from heater H_2 directed toward the second flange and second cold, respectively. They can be formulated as the ratio between the Laplace transform of the temperature response observed in the second flange T_2 or second cold T_1 , and the heater H_2 .

$$G_4 = \frac{L(T_2 - T_{2,0})}{L(Q_2)} = \frac{L\left(0.335 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{132.664}}\right) + 0.058 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{2080.467}}\right)\right)}{L(288 \times 10^{-3} \times 1(t))} = \frac{706.119s + 0.394}{79488.856s^2 + 637.382s + 0.288} \quad (18)$$

$$G_5 = \frac{L(T_1 - T_{1,0})}{L(Q_2)} = \frac{L\left(0.209 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{143.160}}\right) + 5.349 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{525155.694}}\right)\right)}{L(288 \times 10^{-3} \times 1(t))} = \frac{110544.280s + 5.558}{21652168.928s^2 + 151286.070s + 0.288} \quad (19)$$

G_6 and G_7 represent the heat transfer originating from heater H_3 directed toward the third flange and the second flange, respectively. They can be delineated as the ratio between the Laplace transform of the temperature response observed in the third flange T_3 or the second flange T_2 , and the heater H_3 .

$$G_6 = \frac{L(T_3 - T_{3,0})}{L(Q_3)} = \frac{L\left(0.523 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{186.239}}\right) + 0.207 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{622.736}}\right)\right)}{L(22 \times 10^{-3} \times 1(t))} = \frac{364.518s + 0.731}{2551.507s^2 + 17.797s + 0.022} \quad (20)$$

$$G_7 = \frac{L(T_2 - T_{2,0})}{L(Q_3)} = \frac{L\left(0.335 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{132.664}}\right) + 0.058 \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{2080.467}}\right)\right)}{L(22 \times 10^{-3} \times 1(t))} = \frac{706.119s + 0.394}{6072.066s^2 + 48.689s + 0.022} \quad (21)$$

3.2. Simulation model building and verification

According to the response function, the simulink of Matlab software is applied to establish the response model, depicted in Fig. 8. Within this model, the initial temperature fluctuations of the second cold, along with the heat input to the second flange and third flange, are incorporated, alongside the temperature transfer functions. Monitoring nodes are integrated at the second cold, the second flange, the third flange, and the comparison copper block to facilitate the recording of temperature variations throughout the simulation process.

During the experiment, the heater H_2 , located on the second flange, concurrently supplies heat to both the second flange and the second cold. Consequently, in constructing the model, the entire heat cannot be exclusively directed to a particular flange. It must be distributed between them. This heat distribution involves dispersing the temperature rise induced by the heater across the flange. This approach is based on observations derived from the outcomes of the first and second experimental groups. The temperature elevation observed in the second flange predominantly stems from heater H_2 , accounting for approximately 85%, while approximately 15% of this increase originates from heater H_3 . However, concerning the temperature rise in the third flange and the copper block, the contribution is more evenly distributed. Around 54% of the temperature increase is attributed to heater H_2 , whereas approximately 46% is linked to heater H_3 . In the process of constructing the model, the heat distribution pattern must adhere to these proportions. Yet, in cases where the heating

conditions are altered, resulting temperature changes may deviate from these specified ratios. Thus, the allocation ratio must be recalibrated based on the temperature variations induced by the updated heating configuration.

Fig. 8. Response model of “second cold - second flange - third flange - copper block”

Model validation for the thermal response transfer model is conducted within a runtime of 1800s, employing a time step of 0.01s. The temperature responses observed in the second flange, third flange, and comparison copper block are visually presented in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. Simulation results of temperature response

The simulated temperatures of the second cold, the second flange, the third flange, and the comparison copper block are juxtaposed with the experimental findings, as outlined and summarized in Table 5 for comparative analysis.

The analysis of table 5 reveals that when the pulse current is added to the second flange and third flange at the same time in the simulation, the final stabilized temperature of the second cold is 3.763 K, and the temperature fluctuation is 312.11 mK. The final stabilized temperature of the second flange is 4.563 K, and the temperature fluctuation is 5.42 mK. The stabilized temperature of the

third flange is 4.781 K, and the temperature fluctuation is 3.60 mK. The stabilized temperature of copper block temperature is 4.827 K, and the temperature fluctuation is 3.26 mK. The disparity between simulated and experimental values falls within the range of $\pm 0.6\%$, signifying a marginal deviation. Consequently, the model demonstrates reliability, validating its suitability for subsequent simulation studies.

Table 5

Comparison of simulated and experimental temperatures.

Element	Second cold temperature	Second flange temperature	Third flange temperature	Copper block temperature
Experimental value	3.755 K	4.563 K	4.781 K	4.828 K
Simulated value	3.763 K	4.563 K	4.781 K	4.827 K
Absolute deviation	7.94 mK	0.01 mK	0.92 mK	-0.58 mK
Relative deviation	0.21 %	0.0002 %	0.02 %	-0.01 %
Element	Second cold temperature fluctuation	Second flange temperature fluctuation	Third flange temperature fluctuation	Comparison copper block temperature fluctuation
Experimental value	312.10 mK	5.40 mK	3.58 mK	3.25 mK
Simulated value	312.11 mK	5.42 mK	3.60 mK	3.26 mK
Absolute deviation	0.01 mK	0.02 mK	0.02 mK	0.01 mK
Relative deviation	0.003%	0.37%	0.56%	0.31%

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Single stage temperature control

Utilizing the validated model, an active temperature control investigation was conducted, incorporating sinusoidal currents added independently to the second cold, second flange, and third flange. In this simulation, the warming process is temporarily disregarded, focusing only on the attenuation of temperature fluctuations. The primary aim was to determine the optimal current phase (relative to the second cold temperature) and amplitude, aimed at minimizing temperature fluctuations in the copper block. According to the formula (2), taking the second flange as an example, the theoretical optimal amplitude and phase of the current can be obtained, as shown in the following formula.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta Q_0 &= 2\pi fMC\Delta T_1 = 10.82 \times 1.6 \times 0.07 \times 0.156 = 189\text{mW} \\ \varphi &= \varphi_0 + 270^\circ = 270^\circ \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

4.1.1. Optimal phase determination of the active temperature control current

The control variable methodology was employed in the simulation to initially ascertain the optimal current phase. Taking the second cold as an example, the original model served as the basis for introducing a sinusoidal heat input, denoted as ΔQ_{heat} . This input had an average value⁵ of 110mW and amplitude⁶ set at 110mW. The phase of this sinusoidal input ranged from 0 to 360°, illustrated in Fig. 10. It's important to note that the temperature elevation resulting from the increasing ΔQ_{heat} did not surpass 1mK, and thus, was considered negligible in the context of heat distribution.

Utilizing the achieved final stabilized temperature outcomes, the optimal phase for the heating current introduced to the second cold was determined, and the corresponding simulation outcomes are depicted in Fig. 11. To simplify the representation, the phase of the active temperature control current applied to the second cold, second flange, and third flange is expressed by the phase disparity between the current and the temperature of the second cold. As observed in Fig. 11, the optimal

⁵ chosen within a reasonable range to ensure the copper block temperature remains below 5 K, the minimum required for our objective

⁶ matching the average value to prevent negative current values

phase for the current applied to the second cold stands at 270° , same as the theoretical one, resulting in the most minimized temperature fluctuations across the second flange, third flange, and comparison copper block, measuring at 2.26 mK, 1.5 mK, and 1.35 mK, respectively. These values denote a temperature fluctuation suppression rate exceeding 58% at each respective position.

Fig. 10. The thermal response model of Q_{add} added on the second cold

Fig. 11. Temperature fluctuation after adding different phases of temperature control current on the second cold
 During the simulation involving the heating current on the second flange, an amplitude of 200mW was utilized, while modulating the phase from 0 to 360° . The corresponding simulation outcomes are depicted in Fig. 12. It is evident that setting the phase of the additional current on the second flange to 324° , same as the theoretical value calculated from formula (7), leads to the least temperature fluctuations across the second flange, third flange, and comparison copper block, measuring at 5.15 mK, 3.42 mK, and 3.09 mK, respectively. At each respective position, the achieved temperature fluctuation suppression rate exceeds 5%.

Fig. 12. Temperature after adding different phases of temperature control current on the second flange
 During the simulation involving the heating current on the third flange, a current amplitude of 15mW was applied while modulating the phase from 0 to 360° . The resultant simulation outcomes are depicted in Fig. 13. It is evident that setting the phase of the supplementary current on the third flange to 333° , same as the theoretical value calculated from formula (7), results in minimized temperature fluctuations. At this phase, the temperature fluctuations measured at the second cold, second flange, third flange, and comparison copper block are the lowest, recording values of 5.38

mK, 3.39 mK, and 3.07 mK, respectively. This phase configuration yields a temperature fluctuation suppression rate of nearly 0.7% for the second flange and approximately 6% for both the third flange and the comparison copper block.

Fig. 13. Temperature after adding different phases of temperature control current on the third flange

The simulation outcomes indicate that for implementing active temperature control currents at the second cold, second flange, and third flange to regulate temperature, the optimal phase angles for these currents stand at 270°, 324°, and 333°, correspondingly, which are in agreement with the theoretical calculations. Notably, the optimal phase angle progressively increases along the cold flow transfer path due to inherent delays in the cold flow transfer, consequently leading to delayed heat compensation.

4.1.2. Optimal amplitude determination of the active temperature control current

Upon establishing the phase of the active temperature control current, simulations were conducted to ascertain the optimal current amplitude that maximizes temperature fluctuation suppression. Based on the calculated outcome of formula (17), simulations were conducted within proximity to the optimal current amplitude. Operating within a current amplitude range of 0 to 400mW, the simulation outcomes are visually depicted in Fig. 14.

As depicted in Fig. 14, the analysis reveals that setting the current phase at 270° and the amplitude at 190mW yields minimal temperature fluctuations, which aligns well with the theoretical predictions. Specifically, at these parameters, the temperature fluctuations at the second flange, the third flange, and the comparison copper block are notably reduced to 0.275mK, 0.183mK, and 0.166mK, respectively. Relative to their initial temperature fluctuation, the suppression rate can be as high as 94.9%.

Fig. 14. Temperature after adding different amplitude of temperature control current on the second cold

The simulation involved active temperature control currents applied to the second flange and third flange, employing optimal phase values of 324° and 333°, respectively. The amplitude parameters were varied within the ranges of 0 to 220mW and 0 to 20mW, ensuring they remained below the respective pulse current limits of 288mW and 22mW to prevent negative current values. The outcomes of these simulations are depicted in Fig. 15.

Analysis of the outcomes presented in Fig. 15 indicates a discernible improvement in temperature control effectiveness with escalating current levels within the simulated data range. At the peak current, the rate of temperature fluctuation suppression remains approximately 8%. However, due to the imposed upper limit on current, only increasing the current to either the second flange or third flange independently results in significant temperature fluctuations at each respective position, precluding the attainment of an improved temperature control effect.

(1) second flange temperature fluctuation

(2) third flange temperature fluctuation

Fig. 15. Temperature after adding different amplitude current on the second flange and the third flange

Table 6 presents the outcomes of applying active current temperature control individually to the second cold, second flange, and third flange. It details the optimal phase and amplitude values within the temperature control current range, along with the corresponding temperature control effects achieved in each scenario.

Table 6

Optimal phase and amplitude of the current and the temperature control effect of the comparison copper block for single-stage temperature control.

Position	Amplitude	Phase	Copper block Temperature fluctuation	Copper block temperature fluctuation suppression rate
second cold	190 mW	270°	0.166 mK	94.9%
second flange	220 mW	324°	3.076 mK	7%
third flange	20 mW	333°	3.002 mK	8%

Analysis of the data presented in table 6 reveals that in the case of single-stage temperature control, notable suppression effects are observed only at the second cold position. The corresponding attenuation rate is about of 94.9%, which is more than ten-fold better than those values of applying active temperature-control current on the second flange and third flange, the attenuation rates of which are only about 7% and 8%, respectively. To achieve efficient and significant temperature control, the implementation of multi-stage joint temperature control becomes imperative.

4.2. Multistage joint temperature control

In the process of implementing multi-stage joint temperature control, it becomes crucial to sequentially establish the optimal phase and amplitude of the current at each designated position. Leveraging the already established optimal phase of 270° and amplitude of 190 mW for the current applied to the second cold, the next step involves simultaneously introducing temperature control current to the second flange. Given the fixed experimental structure, the phase at each position remains constant throughout the temperature transfer process. Therefore, the optimal phase for incorporating current at the second flange and third flange remains at 324° and 333°, and the focus shifts only towards determining the optimal amplitude under this criterion. The simulation outcomes encompassing amplitudes are displayed in Fig. 16.

The analysis of Fig. 16 indicates that the optimal amplitude for active temperature control heat applied to the second flange and the third flange are determined to be 1.4mW and 0.01mW, respectively. Subsequently, temperature fluctuations at the comparison copper block—measure at 0.153mK and 0.150mK, respectively, under this optimized setting. The addition of active temperature control current to the second flange and the third flange can further reduce the temperature fluctuation at the copper block by nearly 10% (from 0.166 mK to 0.150 mK) compared to the addition of active temperature control current only to the second cold.

Following an analysis of the temperature fluctuation transfer pathway, optimal temperature control parameters are methodically determined, outlining the progression of findings in Table 7.

Table 7 illustrates a clear trend: both single-stage and multi-stage temperature control strategies significantly mitigate temperature fluctuations at each position when compared to the uncontrolled scenario. For instance, focusing on the temperature control effectiveness concerning the comparison copper block, originally fluctuating at 3.26 mK, employing single-stage temperature control on the

second cold achieves a suppression rate of 94.9%. The multi-stage strategy achieves the highest suppression rate, reducing the comparison copper block's temperature fluctuation to 0.150 mK, marking a notable 95.4% attenuation from its initial value.

Fig. 16 Temperature control result in multi-stage joint control

Table 7

Optimal phase and amplitude of the current and the effect of temperature control at each position at different temperature control cases.

Temperature control	Position	Amplitude	Phase	Second flange temperature fluctuation	Third flange temperature fluctuation	Copper block temperature fluctuation	Copper block temperature fluctuation suppression rate
uncontrolled	/	/	/	5.42 mK	3.6 mK	3.26 mK	/
second cold single stage temperature control	second cold	190 mW	270°	0.275 mK	0.183 mK	0.166 mK	94.9%
two-stage joint temperature control	second flange	1.4 mW	324°	0.255 mK	0.169 mK	0.153 mK	95.3%
three-stage joint temperature control	third flange	0.01 mW	333°	0.250 mK	0.166 mK	0.150 mK	95.4%

On the whole, a more effective and straightforward approach involves identifying the optimal phase and amplitude of the temperature control current specifically at the second cold to achieve notable attenuation of temperature fluctuations. In our system, the advantage of multi-level control is not obvious compared with single-stage control on the source of temperature fluctuation, i.e., the second cold head in this work, but for other cryostat, it is necessary to determine the best control stage strategy to meet the requirement of the specific experiments. This can be done with the proposed method in this work, where the best optimal current phases and amplitudes can be estimated from the thermal response experiments.

5. Conclusion

In this work, an active phase and amplitude control method for suppressing temperature fluctuation is developed to provide a high-stable low-temperature working environment, especially for thermodynamic temperature international comparison from 5K to 25K. Based on thermal response experiments, transfer function, thermal response model, and simulation were respectively carried out to finally check the proposed method. The primary conclusions drawn from this study are as follows:

(1) The ultimate stabilized temperatures at each position independent on the heating sequences applied to the heaters on the second flange and third flange, as expected. The simulation results, based on the built transfer function and thermal response model, has a good agreement with thermal

response experiments, the deviation between which fell within $\pm 0.6\%$. This implies the constructed model is reliable and accuracy, therefore increasing our confidence on the further investigation.

(2) For single-stage temperature control, the results show that the simulatively determined optimal current phases and amplitudes agree well with the theoretically calculated values from the proposed method. The optimal phase progressively increases along the cold flow transfer path due to inherent delays in the cold flow transfer, from 270° to 324° and 333° . Besides, applying active temperature-control current on the second cold is the most effective way to mitigate temperature fluctuations on the comparison copper block. The corresponding attenuation rate is about of 94.9%, which is more than ten-fold better than those values of applying active temperature-control current on the second flange and third flange, the attenuation rates of which are only about 7% and 8%, respectively. So, to be simply, applying active temperature-control current on the second cold is good enough for some cases where the temperature fluctuation is relaxed.

(3) Based on the optimal current phases determined by single-stage temperature control, the optimal current amplitudes were further obtained with values of 190mW, 1.4mW, 0.01mW respectively for the three-stage joint temperature control. Compared to the initial copper block temperature fluctuation of 3.26mK without any temperature control, the multi-stage joint temperature control reduced the temperature fluctuation to 0.15mK with an attenuation rate of 95.4%. However, compared to single-stage temperature control on the second cold head, the temperature fluctuation observed at the comparison copper block is reduced from 0.166mK to 0.15mK, improved about 10%. Multi-stage combined temperature control shows slightly superior but with more complex implementation. Consequently, a more simply and straightforward approach involves determining the optimal phase and amplitude of the temperature control current specifically at the second cold to achieve significant attenuation of temperature fluctuations.

The outcomes of this work have potential to be used to realize high-stable low-temperature working environment, especially for thermodynamic temperature data comparisons in future, which will be further studied through experimental verification in subsequent work.

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